

APPLICATION OF A HYBRID SYSTEM OF RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES IN THE SUPPLY OF ELECTRICITY THROUGH A MULTIFUNCTIONAL DEVICE

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An analysis of the main trends in saving non-renewable energy sources at the expense of renewable energy sources on a global scale is presented. The results achieved in the field due to the use of renewable energy sources in a number of countries were reviewed. It is presented that the ways of localization of new technologies in the field of alternative energy in the territory of Uzbekistan and the development of renewable energy sources are considered theoretically. ” the main tasks for realizing the principles of energy and "green" economy are defined. These tasks envisage the saving of annual electricity production, its replacement by "green" energy sources, and the development of renewable energy sources.

In particular, it was emphasized that it is necessary to install solar water heating devices in pre-school educational institutions, schools, higher education institutions and other social sphere objects, and to widely promote the importance of using renewable energy sources, especially solar energy, among the population. Especially in Kashkadarya, Surkhandarya, and Bukhara regions, it was noted that there is a high possibility of using solar energy, and the need to use it effectively.

The experience of developed foreign countries shows that solar energy is a biologically and ecologically safe, renewable energy that can be easily converted into heat and electricity based on methods known in science and can be used

effectively for various purposes in human activities.

Wind and solar hybrid power system

A wind solar supplemental solar energy system uses wind energy and solar energy. It has a history of more than 3000 years. It is ancient and young science, practical and close science, renewable and environmentally friendly. Science and now sustainable development is an industry that has been able to capitalize on it for many years.

In many new energy fields, the development and use of wind energy and solar energy is the first task and is a hot spot in the world today. Because wind and solar energy are used, there is no need for mine, transport, waste, environment. Anti-pollution technology is a near-century project that protects the earth and benefits future generations.

Wind energy and solar energy are important sources of energy with very large reserves in wind energy production systems. Due to seasonal variation and weather changes, wind and solar energy are unstable and intermittent sources of energy. Or, solar photovoltaic energy production has the disadvantages of unstable energy production. However, wind power and solar power have the added natural advantage of strong daytime and nighttime winds; the summer sun is good, the wind is weak, the winter and spring are strong and the sun is weak. The hybrid wind energy system that generates wind energy makes full use of hybrid wind energy and solar energy and is a new energy generation system with high production cost.

Wind energy production is not a problem when there is no wind (especially in the summer months when the nights are long and the nights are short and the sun is strong). In the production of solar photovoltaic energy, there is no sunlight (especially in winter, the night is short, the north wind is big). If no electricity is

produced, wind energy and solar photovoltaic energy can be used to generate continuous energy for 365 days. done. With the continuous improvement of photovoltaic power generation technology and wind power generation technology and the continuous improvement of products in the process of practical use, it has laid the foundation for the introduction and introduction of wind and solar hybrid power generation systems. Ecological scenery, clean, green and environmentally friendly new energy production system will help China to develop energy saving and environmental protection, and help to build a resource-saving and environment-friendly society.

What causes solar panels to lose efficiency?

1.Solar panels use sunlight to create chemical reactions to produce electricity. There is an important causal relationship between power generation and conversion efficiency. People are constantly studying and improving the efficiency of solar panels. What is the efficiency of solar panels? Loss of low energy photon energy. When the photon energy in the solar panel is less than the band gap of the semiconductor, the photon directly penetrates the semiconductor material and does not absorb or generate electron glow pairs, and the energy of the light part is lost about 26%.

2. High energy rays lose energy. When the photon energy is greater than or equal to the band gap of the semiconductor, the photon is absorbed by the semiconductor material, and the energy of the photon is released in the form of heat in the large dry semiconductor band gap, and the fraction of the energy beam is about 40% decreases to

3. Loss of efficiency of absorption and reflection. Semiconductor materials do not have the same absorption capacity for light, and semiconductor materials with a large light absorption coefficient, with a thin thickness of the semiconductor material, have a small photon absorption and a smaller light absorption coefficient. is absorbed. The number of photons is the same. Although incident

photons are active light, they appear as surface reflections. The reason for the surface reflection of a solar panel is that it directly reflects the surface of the electrode on which it is placed. Clarifications related to the difference in refractive index of semiconductor materials and air.

4. Loss of open circuit voltage. Carriers generated by light from a pn junction depend on the electric field of the space charge field, which is the polarization of the charges and the generation of voltage. In a PN junction, it is not possible to extract the energy released through the diffusion potential determined by the doping impurity concentration. This loss is called voltage factor loss, which is about 40%.

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